

Spectrophotometric Determination of Nickel(II) and Palladium(II) by Preliminary Adsorption of their 1-Phenyl-3-(2-thiazolyl)thiourea Complex on Polyurethane Foam

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A new spectrophotometric method for the determination of nickel(II) and palladium(II) after adsorption of their 1-phenyl-3-(2-thiazolyl)thiourea complex on polyurethane foam is discussed. The method has been applied to the determination of nickel(II) in hydrogenated oil and palladium(II) in synthetic samples.

Thiourea and its derivatives exhibit industrial medicinal and analytical applications¹ due to the presence of a functional group $>C=S$ which reacts with cations and anions to give colour reactions of analytical importance. The introduction of substituent at a particular position in a thiourea molecule enhances the analytical stability of the compound.

A selective and sensitive method based on polyurethane foam technique as modified by Bowen² has been developed for the photometric determination of nickel(II) and palladium(II) after adsorption of their 1-phenyl-3-(2-thiazolyl)thiourea (PTT) complex on polyurethane foam. Polyurethane foam technique unlike liquid-liquid extraction, offers low solubility of the extractant, easy separation of phases, easy use of large phase ratios and a synergistic extraction effect. The technique is reproducible and less time-consuming. The present communication describes a sensitive and selective method for the photometric determination of nickel(II) and palladium(II) after adsorption of their 1-phenyl-3-(2-thiazolyl)thiourea complex using polyurethane foam as an adsorbent. Nickel(II) and palladium(II) form coloured water-insoluble complex with PTT solution which is quantitatively adsorbed on prepared polyurethane foam pieces. Survey of the literature reveals report of diverse photometric methods for determination of palladium(II)³ and nickel(II)⁴.

The extraction behaviour of metal complex has been studied with a view to its application to metal determination. The method has been applied for the determination of Ni^{II} in hydrogenated oil and Pd^{II} in synthetic samples.

Results and Discussion

The slope-ratio method⁵ and Job's method⁶ suggest that a 1 : 2 (metal : ligand) complex was formed for both nickel(II) and palladium(II).

The Ni^{II} complex showed maximum absorbance at 440 nm in pH range 2.5–5.5. The system obeyed Beer's law in the range 15–110 $\mu\text{g Ni}$. The sensitivity of the reaction was 0.012 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ of Ni^{II} for 0.001 absorbance and molar absorptivity $1.72 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The effect of diverse

metal ions in the determination of 60 μg of Ni^{II} showed the following tolerance limits (in μg , in parenthesis) : Ag^I, Cu^{II}, Fe^{III}, Al^{III}, Pt^{IV} (100); Pd^{II}, Mn^{II}, Cr^{III}, V^V, U^{VI} (150); Pb^{II} (200).

The Pd^{II} complex at pH 4.5 show maximum absorbance at 488 nm. Beer's law was obeyed in the concentration range 25–180 $\mu\text{g Pd}^{\text{II}}$. The molar absorptivity was found to be $1.56 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and sensitivity 0.020 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ Pd^{II} for 0.001 absorbance. Ten samples containing 110 μg of Pd^{II} gave a mean absorbance of 0.540 with a relative standard deviation of 0.45%. The possible interferences due to the presence of diverse metal ions, i.e. Cu^{II}, Mn^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Bi^{III}, Cr^{III}, Pt^{IV}, Ti^{IV} and V^V containing 110 μg of Pd^{II} were investigated and the metal ions did not interfere.

Application : Hydrogenated oil (0.8 g, Ni 0.001%) sample was heated with 55% HCl (10 ml) for 30 min, in a current of air. The aqueous solution was then separated, concentrated to a small volume, made alkaline with ammonia, boiled and filtered. The coloured filtrate was diluted to a known volume and an aliquot was taken for extraction and spectrophotometric determination of Ni^{II} by the recommended procedure.

Different amounts of metal salts including that of Pd^{II} were mixed in such a way that the resultant mixtures corresponded to some standard reference alloy. The mixture (0.2–0.3 g) was dissolved in aqua regia (25–30 ml) and the solution evaporated to about 5 ml. Concentrated HCl (10 ml) was added to it and the solution warmed. After cooling to room temperature, it was diluted to 500 ml. Interference due to iron was removed by adding 2.0 ml of 5% sodium fluoride (masking agent) to the aliquot of the sample solution and Pd^{II} was determined by the general procedure. The results are given in Table 1.

Experimental

Ethanol solution of 2-aminothiazole (0.01 mol) and phenyl isothiocyanate (0.01 mol) were mixed and refluxed over a water-bath for 5 h. The resulting solid was cooled, washed, dried in air and crystallised from ethanol, brown crystals of 1-phenyl-3-(2-thiazolyl)thiourea, m.p. 108° (Found : C, 51.10; H, 3.79; S, 27.21; N, 17.84%; v_{max} 3240–

3 060 (NH), 1 530 (NH def.), 1 180 (thiocarbonyl), 1 505 cm^{-1} (N-C-N).

TABLE I—DETERMINATION OF PALLADIUM(II) IN SYNTHETIC SAMPLES

Sample	Certified composition%	Amount of Pd ^{II} Taken μg	Amount of Pd ^{II} Found μg	Average (μg) (Error%)
Pt-Ir alloy	Pd, 03.50;	42.50	42.43	42.43 (-0.17)
	Pt, 55.00;		42.39	
	Ir, 28.00,		42.55	
	Rh, 07.00;		42.41	
	Cu, 03.00;		42.40	
	Fe, 03.50*			
Oakay alloy	Pd, 03.50;	64.90	64.77	64.76 (-0.12)
	Ni, 60.00;		64.80	
	Pt, 20.00;		64.62	
	V, 09.50		64.73	
			64.88	

*Masked with 5% NaF.

Stock solution (1000 ppm) of Ni^{II} and Pd^{II} were prepared by dissolving nickel foil in aqua regia and palladium chloride in minimum concentrated HCl respectively and diluted with distilled water. Stock solution was further diluted as required. A 0.2% solution of 1-phenyl-3-(2-thiazolyl)thiourea was prepared in ethanol. Acetate buffer (pH 3–5) was prepared by mixing equal volume of 1 M acetic acid and 1 M ammonium acetate. All chemicals used were of Spectrograde quality.

An EC GS 5701 spectrophotometer and a Systronics 335 pH meter were used for absorbance and pH measurements respectively. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer.

Procedure: Polyurethane foam (Commercial 'U' foam) pieces (~1 cm^3 size) were prepared⁷. A few foam pieces were soaked in 1 M HCl ~10 h to remove possible inorganic contaminants, then pieces were rinsed thoroughly

with distilled water, squeezed and dried in air. The polymeric properties were found to remain intact as a result of these treatments.

To an aliquot of sample solution containing 60 μg of Ni^{II} were added 0.2% PTT solution (2.0 ml) and acetate buffer solution (3.5 ml; pH 4.0). Similarly to an aliquot of sample solution containing 110 μg Pd^{II} a 0.2% reagent solution was added and the pH adjusted to 4.5 using acetate buffer solution (2.5 ml). Both the mixtures were diluted to 10 ml with distilled water and allowed to stand for a few minutes to ensure complete colour formation. To the coloured Ni^{II}-PTT and Pd^{II}-PTT complexes so formed, five and six foam pieces were added respectively, and shaken vigorously to enable the complete adsorption of the metal complex on foam pieces. The foam pieces were then completely squeezed and the complex eluted by squeezing with chloroform (10 ml). Traces of water were removed by adding anhydrous sodium sulphate. Finally, absorbance of the solution was measured at 440 and 488 nm against reagent blank for Ni^{II} and Pd^{II} respectively. The metal contents were measured from the pre-calibrated graph.

References

- O. S. PANWAR and S. P. MATHUR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1994, **71**, 219; M. SATAKE, J. I. MUIRA, SHIROUSAMI and B. K. PURI, *Analyst*, 1989, **114**, 813; D. R. BABU and P. R. NAIDU, *Talanta*, 1991, **38**, 175; S. K. HAWA, B. K. SHARMA, S. P. MATHUR and S. SHARMA, *Oriental J. Chem.*, 1986, **2**, 51.
- H. J. M. BOWEN, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1970, 1082.
- R. KALANI, S. KUMAR and S. P. MATHUR, *Chim. Acta Turcica*, 1994, **22**, 353; S. P. MATHUR, O. S. PANWAR and A. SHARMA, *Chem. Environ. Res.*, 1992, **1**, 99; B. K. PUROHIT, M. CHORDIA, V. MATHUR and S. P. MATHUR, *Afinidad*, 1990, **47**, 427; R. ZABEEN, A. K. GOSWAMI and D. N. PUROHIT, *Asian J. Chem.*, 1994, **6**, 709; J. D. CHAVAN and V. P. JOSHI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1991, **68**, 309.
- M. SHRIVASTAVA and G. S. PANDEY, *J. Inst. Chem.*, 1985, **57**, 55.
- A. E. HARVEY and D. L. MANNING, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 4448.
- P. JOB, *Ann. Chem.*, 1928, **9**, 113.
- R. F. HAMON, A. S. KHAN and A. CHOW, *Talanta*, 1982, **29**, 313.